

Deliverable D3.4 Dissemination of the toolkit across the ERA

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Log of changes

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Table of contents

2. Contribution toward project objectives	2
3. Introduction	4
3.1 Deliverable scope	4
3.2 Relationship with other work packages	4
4. Description of work accomplished	5
4.1 Methodology adopted	5
4.2 RDMkit Website	5
4.3 Branding and the Media Kit	11
4.4 Kick-off Campaign and Social Media Presence	13
4.5 RDMkit Events	14
4.6 Training	15
4.6.1 Training on the RDMkit	16
4.6.2 Training on RDM	18
4.7 Dissemination Activities	20
5. Results	22
6. Conclusions	25
7. Impact	26
7.1 Impact within ELIXIR and the European Research Area	26
7.2 Global Adoption	26
8. Next Steps	28
9. Deviation from Description of Action	28
A. Appendix	29

1. Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable D3.4 of the CONVERGE project and reports on the communication and dissemination activities concerning RDMkit, which is the primary output of WP3. We report the following:

- A brief outline on our approach to RDMkit dissemination, the tools and mediums and the activities that were planned.
- A review of RDMkit sections dedicated to communication, as RDMkit is implemented as a website and, as such, the website itself plays a key role in communication and dissemination activities.
- The branding and visual identity for RDMkit and how this has been developed.
- The Kick Off campaign supporting public release of RDMkit website in March 2021. We also present the social media presence that the RDMkit has had to this date.
- RDMkit events, which are dedicated events for the development of RDMkit and the building and training of its community of contributors.

- Our approach on training RDMkit users on the toolkit itself as well as on RDM topics and tools, we describe in detail how Training information in TeSS and other resources have been integrated into the RDMKit website.
- Workshops, presentations, outreach and awareness raising activities within CONVERGE that were focused on RDMkit or featured an introduction to RDMkit.
- Measured results of dissemination, particularly site analytics for the RDMkit website and visibility indicators for RDMkit in general.

We conclude by discussing the observed impact of RDMkit and the next steps.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1. 2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	Yes

Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	Yes
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	Yes
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	Yes
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	Yes
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	Yes
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	Yes

3. Introduction

3.1 Deliverable scope

[RDMkit](#)¹ is ELIXIR's research data management (RDM) toolkit, and a key output of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. It is an open, community-driven and community-developed resource containing data management guidelines - in line with FAIR principles - for the life sciences. It provides information on how various resources such as standards and software tools can be used for RDM and showcases the RDM best practices adopted in various life science domains. Embedded in its guidelines, RDMkit provides contextualised links to other RDM information resources. RDMkit has been implemented as a website, hereon whenever we use "RDMkit" we refer to the RDMkit website and its contents.

In earlier deliverables we reported:

- the method adopted to build RDMkit and its core structure and operational processes ([D3.1](#)²),
- how RDMkit acts as a single entry point for knowledge and guidance available in various resources in the ELIXIR RDM landscape ([D3.3](#)³),
- extension of the RDMkit best practice guidelines to cover unique data management challenges in the CONVERGE use case demonstrators and the showcasing of domain-specific RDM solutions in the assemblies of tools within RDMkit ([D3.2](#)⁴).

In this deliverable we report on RDMkit's communication and dissemination including its online presence, as well as presentations, workshops, training and publications on RDMkit. We describe the impact that RDMkit has made describing its global adoption by RDM support teams, initiatives and infrastructures. We also describe our planned work to govern the future adoptions of RDMkit.

3.2 Relationship with other work packages

The communication and dissemination activities have been undertaken as follows:

- WP1 Data Management Network developed the RDMkit best practice guidelines and performed the outreach and training activities on RDM and RDMkit.
- WP3 created the RDMkit infrastructure and its operational processes and it mobilised a community around RDMkit. WP3 organised the RDMkit events for dissemination, content development and community orientation/training.

¹<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

²<https://zenodo.org/record/4501634#.ZDfWeOzML0o>

³<https://zenodo.org/record/7707623#.ZDfWg-zML0o>

⁴<https://zenodo.org/record/5139897#.ZDfW2-zML0o>

- WP2 developed RDM training. In addition WP2 curated content in TeSS, ELIXIR training database, which allows RDMkit users to reach relevant training seamlessly from within best practice guidelines.
- WP4 helped in methodology, data collection, communication planning and material, preparation, connections with EC bodies and other policy makers and organisations for outreach activities,
- WP5 (Demonstrators) promoted RDMkit among domain experts while building its content.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Methodology adopted

Prior to its public release we sketched a [communications plan](#)⁵ for the RDMkit, and identified its [goals and scope](#)⁶. These activities allowed us to identify:

- the end users of RDMkit and how we envision the toolkit to help the end users,
- what sets RDMkit apart from other resources as well as what is out of scope for RDMkit,
- strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) for RDMkit as a new online RDM information resource,
- the target groups for the communications as well as communication tools and materials.

RDMkit dissemination activities were tracked in a project-wide reporting sheet established at the beginning of the CONVERGE project.

4.2 RDMkit Website

The RDMkit website not only delivers the toolkit functionality and contents, but also provides a medium for communication. The “About” section of the RDMkit website is dedicated to communication purposes; a screenshot of the overview page for this section is given in Figure 1. The “About” section is composed of a “Community” subsection as well as individual pages on “Contact information”, “News”, “Events”, “Outreach” activities and finally the “Media kit”.

⁵https://docs.google.com/document/d/1XECuvDB1pYsCloXCrS_kzecz-R_jpJDB1vB7ZwHOgGLs/edit#heading=h.nsjp2gw5e8cw

⁶<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1OrVMACTFT1-BD-SH0SRmwkhON8zcKC19Ov57sdPuUB0/edit#heading=h.k6fci9740nx3>

Figure 1. Overview page of the RDMkit “About” section.

In the “Community” section we showcase the RDMkit community, which comprises content contributors, editors and RDMkit development leads. Each contributor is acknowledged with their name, optionally a profile photo/avatar, institutional affiliation, contact information (email, ORCID and Github handles) are provided. Also in this section, the RDMkit editorial board is presented, as shown in Figure 2, the process to be followed to become an editor is also described. Furthermore the funders, research infrastructures and institutions that have supported RDMkit development are acknowledged in the support page.

Figure 2. Page that introduces the RDMkit editorial board.

The main contact point for RDMkit inquiries is the RDMkit editorial board, the website provides a contact page with an email to reach the board. The media kit for RDMkit is made available for download from its dedicated page, we discuss the contents of the media kit and its development in Section 4.3.

RDMkit is a live resource with new guidelines and tools added continuously. We inform RDMkit users on toolkit updates via the news page, given in Figure 3. Updates could be:

- addition of a new page on an RDM topic,
- page/site re-designs,
- new site functionality such as a new button on pages to view recent changes,
- a new integration to another RDM resource.

Figure 3. Page for announcing recent updates on the RDMkit website.

On the events page we announce the recent past and upcoming RDMkit events to inform the community and to invite them for participation. A screenshot of this page is given in Figure 4; we describe dedicated RDMkit events in detail in Section 4.5.

The screenshot shows the RDMkit website interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Data management', 'About', 'Contribute', and 'GitHub', along with a search bar. A left sidebar menu lists 'About', 'Community', 'Contact', 'News', 'Events' (highlighted), 'Media kit', 'Outreach', 'Accessibility', and 'Privacy'. The main content area is titled 'Events' and lists three past events:

- RDMkit Contentathon**: 22 May 2023 9:00 - 24 May 2023 12:00 CET, Monasterium, Ghent, Belgium + virtual. Description: 'As a community, we want to make sure that the RDMkit content is regularly revised, improved, and further developed for better learning of what data management entails and how it works. With that, we would like to invite current and future contributors to [join us](#) at RDMkit contentathon!'
- Contentathon**: 23 June 2021 9:00 - 24 June 2021 13:30 CET, Online. Description: 'We would like to invite you to highlight your set of data management tools as a tool assembly in the RDMkit and describe how to use it, so others can do the same (two half days). [Sign up here](#).'
- BioHackathon Europe**: 08 November 2021 - 12 November 2021, Barcelona. Description: 'Highlight your data management tool assembly in the RDMkit! Highlight your data management tools assembly in the RDMkit!'

Figure 4. Page for announcing RDMkit events in the recent past and upcoming future.

On the outreach page, displayed in Figure 5, we showcase selected RDMkit dissemination activities and make available their materials i.e. slides and video recordings. This page does not provide the full list of dissemination activities, instead it highlights those RDMkit communications that were targeted to distinct audiences e.g. data stewards, developers of other online guides or research data infrastructures beyond Europe. The full list of dissemination activities and their summary is given in Section 4.7.

The screenshot shows the RDMkit website at rdmkit.elixir-europe.org. The navigation bar includes 'Data management', 'About', 'Contribute', and 'GitHub', along with a search bar. A left sidebar under 'About' lists 'Community', 'Contact', 'News', 'Events', 'Media kit', 'Outreach' (highlighted), 'Accessibility', and 'Privacy'. The main content area is titled 'Outreach' and contains a list of presentations:

- Presentations
- Videos

Below the list, a paragraph states: 'We are, since the beginning, actively spreading the word about RDMkit making sure it reaches a wider audience across the globe. On this page, we keep track of where RDMkit has been presented so far and the relevant links.'

The 'Presentations' section lists three events:

- RDM Knowledge Source (RDMkit) - Data Stewardship Interest Group (DSIG) meeting**
2023-01-12
RDMkit was introduced to the DSIG at one of their monthly meetings, together with introduction on IDTkit and FAIRCookBook. [Presentation slides on RDMkit \(PDF\)](#).
- ELIXIR FAIR & Research Data Management know-how ecosystem - All hands 2022**
2022-06-10
RDMkit was presented at all hands. The presentation can be found on [f1000 research](#)
- Q-EBRA WORKSHOP: Your next grant application - methodological approach**
2022-04-27
The event involved different activities on how to write a grant application and DMP generation, including a talk about RDMkit and an eLearning session on how to use the Data Stewardship Wizard. [More information about the event](#)

Figure 5. Page listing selected outreach activities RDMkit events in the recent past and upcoming future.

Finally, the RDMkit landing page features various pages in the “About” section that are dedicated to RDMkit communications and orientation. As seen in Figure 6, the contributors page and contribution guide, site updates, RDMkit events and community and content statistics are all featured on the RDMkit landing page.

Figure 6. Section on the RDMkit Landing page that features site contributors and contribution guide, site updates, RDMkit events and finally key RDMkit statistics.

4.3 Branding and the Media Kit

The RDMkit brand name was chosen by the RDMkit community in a vote among the participants of the January 2021 contentathon. The logo and the visual identity for the RDMkit have been built through an iterative process. The Communications Officer at the ELIXIR Hub (Xenia Perez Sitja at the time, now ELIXIR UK), together with members of the editorial team (Bert Droesbeke, Martin Cook), prepared multiple designs and the editorial board gave feedback and did the final selection.

RDMkit visuals include a logo and a data lifecycle diagram. The logo has a standard and a compact version, as given in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7. The RDMkit logo.

Figure 8. Compact version of the RDMkit logo.

Within the RDMkit visuals we also have the data life cycle diagram, which is displayed in Figure 9. The life cycle diagram is frequently used by ELIXIR Nodes and others beyond ELIXIR within their RDM training materials and online guidelines.

Figure 9. The RDMkit data life cycle diagram.

The [media kit page](#)⁷ of the RDMkit website provides downloads of the logo, the compact logo and the lifecycle diagram with the inverted versions in SVG and PNG formats. In addition, the media kit includes single-slide and three-slide introductory presentations on RDMkit, for those who would like to include RDMkit in their presentations. We also provide promotional gif to be used in social media posts.

4.4 Kick-off Campaign and Social Media Presence

To announce the release of RDMkit within and beyond ELIXIR we ran a kick-off campaign, which included the following communication activities:

- On the 1st of March 2021 the RDMkit internal release was announced via an [ELIXIR Webinar](#)⁸. The live webinar had 56 attendees and its recording had 92 views to date on YouTube.
- On the 31st of March 2021 the RDMkit public release was announced;
 - with a Twitter post from ELIXIR, including a 0:40 seconds [promotional video](#)⁹, which had 1,344 views,
 - with [a news release from ELIXIR](#)¹⁰, which had 600 unique page views.
- Between February 2021 and January 2023, RDMkit was mentioned 15 times on ELIXIR Weekly Briefs (internal newsletters) which has 839 recipients and average open rate >40%.

Since the release of RDMkit in March 2021, 17 tweets and 4 LinkedIn posts related to the RDMkit were published. The first post published on Twitter was the announcement of the release of RDMkit, it had more than 3,000 impressions and 42 engagements, which resulted in 1.2% engagement rate (usually a good engagement rate is between 1% to 5%¹¹).

RDMkit was also mentioned in several social media campaigns, including World Health Day and Open Access Week. On World Health Day in 2021, ELIXIR published a tweet to highlight the RDMkit's section that is dedicated to data management in human research. During Open Access Week, two tweets were published to emphasise RDMkit's contribution to open data.

As a key resource developed throughout ELIXIR-CONVERGE, RDMkit was also present in social media activity of different events, such as the 2021 ELIXIR All Hands Meeting, ELIXIR outreach webinars and 2022 BioHackathon Europe. The RDMkit was tagged and mentioned in the posts promoting these events and has also received a good amount of engagement rate.

⁷https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/media_kit

⁸<https://elixir-europe.org/events/webinar-rdmkit>

⁹<https://twitter.com/ELIXIREurope/status/1377290405084024834?s=20>

¹⁰<https://elixir-europe.org/news/elixir-converge-rdmkit>

¹¹https://blog.hootsuite.com/calculate-engagement-rate/#What_is_engagement_rate

4.5 RDMkit Events

Community events play a key role in RDMkit’s development and the forming and training of its community. We have had dedicated RDMkit events of the following types:

- RDMkit contentathons, where community members write RDMkit guidelines and pages with the help of editors.
- RDMkit hackathons and editors face-2-face meetings, where RDMkit editors review GitHub issues on site usability, function and content and discuss/develop solutions.
- RDMkit projects in Biohackathons where RDMkit editors meet up with experts in other domains to improve RDMkit usability, content and function such as integration to other resources.
- RDM workshops in ELIXIR All Hands Meetings, where RDMkit is presented to the wider ELIXIR community and feedback is collected.

Table 1 below summarises all dedicated RDMkit events that have been held during the course of the CONVERGE project.

Table 1 RDMkit Events.

2020 June	ELIXIR AHM RDM Workshop	Presentation of the result of the ELIXIR-wide RDM tools stock taking.
2020 July	Hackathon	Bootstrapping of the toolkit website, drafting of operational processes
2020 October	Contentathon	Content development on RDM lifecycle stages, tasks, domain and roles.
2021 January	Contentathon	Content development in various RDMkit sections, content gap analysis.
2021 May	Contentathon	Content development in various RDMkit sections, content gap analysis.
2021 June	Contentathon	Content development on domain and tool assembly pages, content gap analysis.

2021 June	ELIXIR AHM RDM Workshop	User Experience (UX) assessment of the RDMkit website.
2021 November	Biohackathon	Project for writing RDMkit pages on national resources and exemplar tool assemblies. UX expert's assessment of the RDMkit website.
2022 November	Biohackathon	Project for improving RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook integration.
2022 December	Editors F2F, Hackathon, Contentathon	Review of possible site structure and functionality improvements. Content review and development in various RDMkit sections.
2023 May	Editors F2F, Hackathon, Contentathon	Review of possible site structure and functionality improvements. Content review and development in various RDMkit sections.

We widely announced RDMkit events, particularly the contentathons. We used project mailing lists and Slack channels to invite participants from all work packages and all use case demonstrators of the CONVERGE project. Events were featured in the ELIXIR newsletter as well as the Nodes' own communication mediums such as newsletters and social media accounts. In addition we have reached out to ELIXIR Communities for their participation.

4.6 Training

Training, as an RDMkit dissemination activity, had two components:

- (1) training on the RDMkit website that would allow researchers and data stewards to use RDMkit and to enhance it. We refer to this as "training on RDMkit";
- (2) training on the RDM topics and tools included in RDMkit, which would allow researchers to plan and execute their data management. We refer to this as "training on RDM".

In the subsections that follow we elaborate on how we addressed these two training needs.

4.6.1 Training on the RDMkit

In the project proposal we had envisioned the development of dedicated material and training on the RDMkit. During the course of the project, we observed that research data management is a complicated endeavour on its own, and we should lower the barrier of use as much as possible for RDMkit users. As a result, we developed RDMkit as a self-explanatory, easy-to-use website, eliminating the need for training as a prerequisite to start using the toolkit.

To understand and improve RDMkit site usability, we collected user and expert assessments. Shortly after RDMkit's public release, in the RDM Workshop at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in June 2021, we organised an [RDMkit User Experience \(UX\) assessment session](#)¹². We performed structured interviews with RDMkit users in various personas, including funders, researchers, and data stewards. We asked users their impressions of the RDMkit landing page, some of the topic-specific pages and the tools/resources table. We gave users small tasks such as finding information or tools on a particular topic on the website. We recorded user feedback as they navigated through the website to complete the task. In addition, at the BioHackathon in November 2021, we asked [UX experts for feedback on the RDMkit landing page](#)¹³. The feedback from both workshops was then translated into improvements on the website.

RDMkit is a community-driven resource. Every RDMkit user is also potentially a contributor to the RDMkit. Empowering users to become contributors requires training them about the structure and operational processes of RDMkit. We achieved this by (1) developing a contributors guide and making it part of the RDMkit, (2) organising contentathons where we trained RDMkit beginners on the job, so to speak. During contentathons we worked in small content development teams each led by an RDMkit editor. In these teams we gave novice contributors small tasks, we pointed them to the contributor's guide and gave them the opportunity to ask questions to other contributors and editors.

A screenshot of the overview page of RDMkit's "Contribute" section is given in Figure 10. RDMkit's infrastructure and content is open source and is maintained on GitHub. The online contribution guide describes the different means and tools with which content can be authored and submitted. For each contribution path the documentation provides step by step guidance with screenshots of each step.

- For users not familiar with Git, the website offers google doc templates to assist the writing of content.
- For users familiar with Git it is possible to use the GitHub GUI, or the Git command interface directly.
- Recording RDM tools in RDMkit tool inventory can be done by providing information either through google docs or via the Git(Hub) interfaces.

¹²<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1tRyknslvQLdJz1lDiFez9SYx33ex1p7>

¹³<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1voKjx6trkDLvwFDIBnH9u07EJyZpXyqbVbaM5cygrmY/edit#heading=h.fg0ux0hduehdh>

Figure 10. Overview of the RDMkit “Contribute” section.

The “Contribute” section also includes:

- A writing style guide to ensure content across various RDMkit sections and pages is delivered in a harmonised language.
- A brief copyright guideline to inform contributors on how they should quote and refer to guidance in other resources as well as imagery/icons and the licensing issues that they should pay attention to.
- A cheatsheet for Markdown, the lightweight page syntax in which RDMkit content is written, as well as a documentation of page metadata attributes should have. These attributes help with (1) the search engines’ indexing of pages and (2) the RDMkit site infrastructure to auto generate appropriate cross links between RDMkit pages and between RDMkit and other RDM information resources such as the DSW and the FAIR Cookbook.
- A checklist and a guide for editors of the RDMkit website. RDMkit content goes through editorial review prior to its publishing, this section will advise editors on the review expected of them as well as the process they should follow to interact with.

- A code of conduct for the entire RDMkit community: users, contributors and editors,; which clarifies how we expect all members of the community to treat each other and puts processes in place to report and deal with unacceptable behaviour.

4.6.2 Training on RDM

Training is a key element, which, combined with the RDM best practices and tools, results in increased data management and stewardship capacity for RDMkit's users. The CONVERGE project includes, in WP2, the development and delivery of RDM training programmes by the ELIXIR nodes. Nodes' RDM training material and events are made available through [TeSS](#)¹⁴, ELIXIR's one-stop shop for trainers and trainees to discover online information and content, including training materials, events and interactive tutorials, as well as other resources such as Youtube, Zenodo and GitHub. RDMkit integrates, in its guidelines, the information available in these and other training resources. Specifically, RDMkit provides:

- a thematic "Trainings" box in each best practice guideline page;
- a dedicated page for the combined list of "All training resources" from all RDMkit pages;
- links to training on tools included in RDMkit.

Thematic "Trainings" box

Each RDMkit best practice guideline page has a "Training" segment, where links to TeSS and other training resources can be found, see bottom left in Figure 11. RDMkit pages are linked to TeSS in two ways. First is the default TeSS link, which is available on all pages. This link launches a search on TeSS with the keywords capturing that current page's topic. Another recommended way is to link to TeSS's collections, which are thematic groups of training material. A third way to link to training is to provide links to external resources as illustrated in Figure 11.

¹⁴<https://tess.elixir-europe.org>

Figure 11. “Training” segment in the RDMkit Human Data domain page, which illustrates different means of linking to training information.

“All training resources” page.

RDMkit provides a dedicated page, illustrated in Figure 12, to provide a searchable list of all training resources included in all RDMkit best practice guideline pages.

Figure 12. “All training resources” page in RDMkit.

Links to training in the “Tools and resources” table.

RDMkit best practice guidelines show how various tools can be used to solve RDM challenges. Tools are listed on the guideline pages in a table view at the bottom of the page; Figure 13 provides an example. In the “Registry” column of the tools table a link to TeSS will be provided if training information concerning the tool is available.

Relevant tools and resources

Tool or resource ⓘ	Description	Related pages	Registry ⓘ
BBMRI-ERIC's ELSI Knowledge Base	The ELSI Knowledge Base is an open-access resource platform that aims at providing practical know-how for responsible research.	Data protection Sensitive data Data Steward: policy Data Steward: research	
Beacon	The Beacon protocol defines an open standard for genomics data discovery.	Researcher Data Steward: research Data Steward: infrastructure	i Tool info Standards/Databases Training

Figure 13. A excerpt of the “Relevant tools and resources” table on the RDMkit Human Data page. One of the tools listed is the Genomics data discovery Beacon, for which a TeSS training link is provided. The existence of the link indicates that a TeSS search on Beacon returns information on training materials and/or events.

Integration of training information into RDMkit has been achieved through a collaboration with WP2. Specifically, we organised 2 workshops where we focused on:

- (1) increasing the findability of Nodes’ RDM training by registering them in TeSS, and then, annotating the TeSS records by descriptive keywords - we used the EDAM ontology and the RDMkit page tags.
- (2) updating RDMkit pages to include links pointing to the newly established TeSS records.

4.7 Dissemination Activities

RDMkit dissemination began before the official release of RDMkit website in March 2021 (the list of events was provided in [D3.1](#)¹⁵ section 4.4). At the time of release, communities had already been notified and it gave a good start. Further dissemination was intensive and involved all the partners, ranging from WP leads and RDMkit contributors to data stewards.

A summary of RDMkit dissemination activities is presented in Figures 14 and 15. The most productive year was 2021, which included 50 recorded events. The next year was still strong with 47 recorded occurrences. In total for the duration of the project, there were more than 115 dissemination events. The majority of activities were presentations at different events and auditories (46%), followed by workshops (17%). Written pieces, webinars, courses and other

¹⁵<https://zenodo.org/record/4501634#.ZDfWeOzML0o>

activities constituted the remaining 36%.

Dissemination highlights include:

- **USA:** The RDMkit has been presented at events chaired by the NIH ODSS, including: ISMB/ECCB 2021 FAIR Session, NIH ODSS Webinar 2022, and BioITWorld FAIR Data symposium 2023. The RDMkit was also presented at a major National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine workshop on Changing the Culture of Data Management and Sharing (2021) to prepare the USA for the NIH Data Sharing mandate in 2023.
- **European Commission:** the RDMkit was invited to present at an internal EC workshop: "FAIR workshop for European Commission Project and Policy Officers" in 2021.
- **Hong Kong:** 5 hours of presentation and workshop delivered online in the University of Hong Kong Research Integrity workshop, day 1 focusing on staff and day 2 on students (2022).

Figure 14. RDMkit dissemination activities per year.

Figure 15. RDMkit dissemination activities per type

Finally, we have completed the writing of an RDMkit paper, which we plan to submit for peer review before the end of the CONVERGE project.

5. Results

Google Analytics is a powerful tool that can be used to measure the success of our dissemination efforts. There are several ways in which Google Analytics can demonstrate the accomplishment of this task.

One of the most basic metrics is website traffic. Figure 16 presents the daily RDMkit website traffic and cumulative number of new users. The graph exhibits a weekly pattern with a lower number of visits on weekends. Additionally, there are periods of reduced activity during the Christmas vacation, while several highly pronounced peaks were observed on specific dates such as 31 March 2021 (corresponding to the public release of the website), 15 May 2021 and 14 February 2022. On average, the daily number of new users is 22 individuals. As illustrated in Figure 17, the geographic spread of RDMkit users is the entire globe with the top most countries being the USA, the UK, Germany, Netherlands, France, Finland and Norway.

Figure 16. Number of RDMkit website users over time

Figure 17. Number of users by country

Another metric is how users come to the RDMkit website. As demonstrated on Figure 18, 51.9% of new users arrive via a direct link; 9.8% arrive from other websites without utilising Google search; 1.4% arrive via regular posts and profile links on social media platforms and 36.8% originate from organic search. Organic search results are the unpaid listings that appear on Google search engine because it's relevant to someone's search terms.

Figure 18. Source of new users

Top 10 keywords for Google searches leading to RDMkit visits are the following (the most popular is on top):

1. rdmkit
2. rdm kit
3. rdm toolkit
4. markdown cheat sheet
5. research data steward
6. data reuse
7. data management plan tool
8. rdm-kit
9. dmp tools
10. reuse of data

Interesting that “markdown cheat sheet” is in 4th place, immediately after different spellings of RDMkit. This cheat sheet is part of the contribution guide described in Section 4.6 of this deliverable.

Google analytics also provides information about the interest of RDMkit users. Figure 19 illustrates this interest by plotting the number of views per top 10 RDMkit pages. Unsurprisingly, 7 out of 8 main topics presented on RDMkit landing page are in this list. However, “Your role” and “All training resources” are not in the list. “Your role” page (12th of the most visited) and “All training materials” (14th place) thus are not listed here. Interestingly, among the top 10 most visited pages are “Data

lifecycle: planning” and “Your task: DMP” pages that indicates RDMkit highly used at the planning stage of research activities.

Further investigation of RDMkit user interest reveals that the most visited domain pages are “Biomolecular simulation data” (1052 views), Human data (971 view) and Plant sciences (797 views). The most visited task pages are “Data management plan” (1499 views), “Documentation and metadata” (1297 views) and “Data organisation” (819 views).

Figure 19. The most visited RDMkit pages

An additional important metric for assessing the efficacy of dissemination initiatives is the frequency with which RDMkit website is cited as a source by other online resources. Specifically, RDMkit has been referenced by a total of 200 distinct web domains, encompassing:

- 7 ELIXIR nodes;
- 8 funding agencies;
- 65 university and research institutes, among which are globally renowned entities such as Yale University, University of Oxford and MIT.

6. Conclusions

RDMkit is one of the many outputs of the CONVERGE project. The dissemination for RDMkit was performed in concert with the dissemination of all results of the CONVERGE project. Members of all WPs as well as the leadership teams participated in the dissemination activities. Our activities included:

- awareness raising on the challenges of RDM in the lifesciences,
- informing all stakeholders on RDMkit scope, goals and features,

- building the RDMkit community, orienting RDMkit users to become contributors,
- keeping the RDMkit community informed and engaged,
- promoting the RDMkit, announcing our achievements and plans.

This deliverable reported the evidence for the above listed activities and the results obtained in terms of RDMkit visibility and website presence. In the remainder of the deliverable we discuss RDMkit's impact and the future plans for RDMkit.

7. Impact

7.1 Impact within ELIXIR and the European Research Area

RDMkit's impact became evident within the lifetime of the CONVERGE project. Following its public release, the RDMkit has been included in the European Commission's [Horizon Europe Programme Guide](#)¹⁶ for grantees and the [ERC Guidelines](#)¹⁷ for grantees as a “resource for Data Management guidelines and good practices for the Life Sciences”. This represents a clear endorsement of the resource by important funders of the life sciences.

Within ELIXIR, the RDMkit has become a “Node service” for the nodes of Belgium, Norway, Sweden and UK. The services offered by these nodes include one or more of the following:

- Support and further development of RDMkit's website infrastructure, [the ELIXIR Toolkit Theme \(ETT\)](#)¹⁸. The ETT, which was initially developed to support the RDMkit, is a template for the Jekyll website generator has proven to be a popular component on its own. The ETT source code repository is the most starred/forked project in the ELIXIR Organisation on GitHub.
- Content maintenance and development for [the main RDMkit website](#)¹⁹.
- Content development for local RDM guidelines that are to be deployed using the ETT such as [this RDM signpost website from ELIXIR Norway](#)²⁰.

7.2 Global Adoption

RDMkit has been adopted by many teams globally through one or more of the following:

- (1) the re-use of RDMkit's re-usable site infrastructure, i.e. the ELIXIR Toolkit Theme,
- (2) the re-use of the RDMkit content,
- (3) the adoption of the approach that RDMkit takes to provide online guidance.

¹⁶https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

¹⁷https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document-Open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf

¹⁸<https://github.com/ELIXIR-Belgium/elixir-toolkit-theme>

¹⁹<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>

²⁰<https://elixir.no/rdm-lookup/>

Table 2 below summarises the known adoptions of RDMkit. This represents clear evidence of the impact of this work, since adoption is by projects, initiatives and consortia that are beyond ELIXIR. Furthermore, there is an element of cost-savings and efficiency to highlight, since adopters do not need to reinvent the wheel - this is particularly important given that the RDMkit was funded by the public purse.

Table 2. Adoptions of RDMkit.

Country	Team	Adoption
International	FAIRDOM consortium of services for Research Data Management https://fair-dom.org/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
Australia	Australian BioCommons https://www.biocommons.org.au/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
Belgium	Applied Bioinformatics and BioStatistics https://intranet.psb.ugent.be/abb/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
Belgium	RDM Guide from ELIXIR Belgium https://rdm.elixir-belgium.org/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
International	Infectious Diseases Toolkit https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme and RDMkit Approach
Australia	Human omics data sharing "field guide" https://australianbiocommons.github.io/human-omics-data-sharing-field-guide	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
Australia	ABLES https://australianbiocommons.github.io/ables/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
International	Workflowhub About https://about.workflowhub.eu/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
Germany	NFDi4Chem Consortium for Research Data Management in Chemistry https://www.nfdi4chem.de/	RDMkit Approach "We were so impressed by ELIXIR-Converge's RDMKit that we adopted its architecture as a starting point."
Holland	ERASMUS University https://eur-nl.github.io/erim-rdmkit/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme and RDMkit content

Norway	ELIXIR Norway https://elixir.no/rdm-lookup/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
International	1+MG Trust Framework https://rajxir.github.io/oneplusmg-trust-framework/	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme and RDMkit Approach

In late 2022 a representative of the NIH Office of Data Strategy joined the RDMkit editorial board.

8. Next Steps

RDMkit is part of a larger landscape of RDM resources, all of which are transitioning from formation into maturity. This landscape a.k.a. “the ELIXIR RDM ecosystem”²¹ includes knowledge resources such as the RDMkit, the Data Stewardship Wizard and the FAIR Cookbook, as well as the community that builds and uses these resources. The resources need the community to thrive, whereas the community needs the resources in order to capture RDM knowledge in a systematic, exploitable and scalable manner to reach the goal of FAIR RDM for the life sciences. Due to tight inter-dependency of the resources and the community, the sustainability of the ELIXIR RDM Ecosystem needs to be considered as a whole. For this purpose, we will organise a day-long workshop at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in June 2023 to develop sustainability plans for the ELIXIR RDM Ecosystem.

The adoptions of RDMkit by various research and RDM-support teams has revealed a need to govern future adoptions. We started working on the concept of an “RDMkit Alliance”, which will form a framework for cooperation and governance between adopters of RDMkit, and layout the rules for attribution for the re-users of RDMkit infrastructure and/or content.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable

²¹ The [Data Management \(DM\) Network](#) of WP1 is another key output of the CONVERGE project, alongside RDMkit. The network has now become the foundation for an emerging ELIXIR community, named the Research Data Management (RDM) Community. In their whitepaper the RDM community identifies, for itself, “the management of RDM knowledge and know-how in the form of the content of the ELIXIR RDM ecosystem” as a key responsibility.

A. Appendix

Table of [Dissemination activities \(w RDMkit filter²²\)](#).

Table of RDMkit [twitter activity highlights²³](#).

Table of [Websites that link to RDMkit²⁴](#).

²²https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/10GNHLElusi99BpT63NGeh_qRY9cMpKUBmVEGiolLumQ/edit#gid=1159678595

²³<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/12GektPodilVb3lUhwWdWMIBNaxO1sWmhYZ6dFdzk380/edit#gid=0>

²⁴<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1RfgY4yxXlZhiYYVV-IJtp2EQ5bqji9Ss9IHJOqf6OAw/edit#gid=1702293238>

